

Effect of Art Based Therapy on Loneliness among Adolescents in Selected Junior Colleges

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ABSTRACT

INTRODUCTION

Adolescents are prone to loneliness; the challenge of dealing with social and academic pressures, as well as navigating the developmental changes between childhood and adulthood, will be very difficult for many adolescents. The way people interact with one another has been radically changed by the Internet and other digital communications in the 21st century. It is necessary to pay special attention to recognizing loneliness among adolescents because the public health burden of loneliness in later life could be reduced with better understanding of the phenomenon.

NEED FOR STUDY

The prevalence of loneliness was observed in adolescents aged between 12 and 17 years in 76 countries at 9.2%-14.4%. According to the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development, the mean levels of loneliness experienced at school among adolescents aged 15-16 have risen significantly between 2012 to 2018. By adopting corrective measures, adolescents can reduce the burden of loneliness in later life.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

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OBJECTIVES

1. To assess the loneliness among adolescents
2. To evaluate the effect of Art Based Therapy on loneliness among adolescents

METHODOLOGY

Quasi experimental study; Simple Random sampling was used to select 30 subjects each for experimental and control group. Loneliness was measured by Loneliness Assessment Scale. 21 sessions of Art Based Therapy including 11 sessions of altered magazine photo and 10 sessions of crumpled paper painting was conducted for subjects in study group. Each session was lasting for 45 minutes, thrice in a week. Pre and post test only conducted for control group.

RESULTS

Adolescents who received Art-Based Therapy were able to express themselves more freely, analyse their feelings, and feel closer to others. Thus, a decrease in adolescent loneliness was seen. Results indicated that Mean post-test of loneliness scores (20.97) was less than pre test scores (36.17). The *p* value is <0.0001 which shows Art Based Therapy is highly effective in reducing loneliness among adolescents.

CONCLUSION

Art Based Therapy effectively reduced loneliness among adolescents. The valuable insights provided by this study can be used to guide future research, practice, and policy-making on reducing adolescent loneliness.

KEYWORDS: Loneliness, Art Based Therapy, Adolescents, Junior colleges

INTRODUCTION

The feeling of loneliness is an unwelcome emotional response to the perception of isolation. It is also referred to as social pain, which is a psychological mechanism which motivates individuals to seek social connections. The perception of loneliness is often associated with a feeling of disconnectedness and intimacy. Loneliness is a social affliction that is universal and is felt by all regardless of one's race, gender, age, or cultural background. Adolescents have been reported to be the most prone to loneliness.

Omar Al Omari^[1] reported that the frequency of experiencing loneliness was 1 (0.1%), 625 (59.1%), 429 (40.6%), and 2 (0.2%), which are considered low, moderate, moderately high, and high experiences for loneliness, respectively. The prediction of loneliness was significantly influenced by previous depression or anxiety, dissatisfaction with life and depression.

Christina R. Victor^[2] observed that individuals who are under 25 years old and those who are over 65 years old exhibit the highest levels of loneliness. In young and middle-aged years, loneliness is linked to poor physical health, but not in later years.

The discrepancy between desired and achieved level of interaction is a source of negative emotions linked to loneliness, as indicated by another study and a person's vulnerability to loneliness can be exacerbated by genetic predispositions that impact certain personality traits and behaviors which forms relationships. (Perlman and Peplau 1981)

Fardghassemi & Joffe^[3] correctly stated that loneliness is acknowledged as a global public health issue that is most prevalent during adolescence. In spite of being surrounded by multiple opportunities for networking and social interaction, the perception of many adolescents and young adults today is that they have nobody to turn to. The way adolescents and young adults deal with social connections may determine whether they feel lonely or not. In an effort to decrease their risk of emotional loneliness, older adults may prioritize close family relationships; adolescents may neglect their emotional needs and experience loneliness by focusing on increasing social connections.

Loneliness during adolescence can have a negative impact on mental health, including depression, aggression or suicidal thoughts (World Health Organization, 2018). Adolescents and young adults who experience loneliness have a high prevalence of poor self-rated health. Loneliness, mental and physical health problems are linked to risky health behaviors in this age group. Sakiz et al^[4] proved that low self-esteem and loneliness are associated. Loneliness is particularly harmful for adolescents and young adults, even when it is correlated with an external locus of control because they may have the belief that they are not in charge of the outcome. This

can result in poor social skills and a general mindset that can inhibit social interactions with others.

Yulia Korzhina et al^[5] revealed that adolescents and young adults with chronic physical disease reported a higher rate of social isolation, low social peer acceptance and having less friends. Adolescents and young adults with heart disease reported that depression and loneliness can be mutually reinforcing and predictive.

It has been observed that insecure family relationships can lead to involuntary loneliness among adolescents. Vaarala et al^[6] observed that Social life during childhood could be hindered by an authoritative home upbringing, parental alcoholism, home culture of silence and absent parental listening and it is conceivable that it could lead to a feeling of loneliness in later life.

Chen & Qin^[7] found that adolescents who faced traumatic environments or childhood bullying were found to be at a higher risk of anxiety and major depressive disorders and often experience loneliness. Cyberbullying has been observed to have the potential to cause young individuals to encounter different psychosocial adjustment issues such as loneliness, anxiety and depression. Adolescents might use social media to compensate for their lack of social connections by sharing both online and offline information. Furthermore, these actions could have a connection to negative/destructive coping techniques.

It is crucial to identify the causes underlying loneliness and to pay special attention to mitigate the negative effects of loneliness among adolescents. Therefore, they can lessen the burden of loneliness in later life by having a better understanding of the remedial measures.

MATERIALS & METHODS

This is a quantitative approach; quasi experimental study was conducted among adolescents aged 15 – 19 years in junior colleges.

Sample size

Two junior colleges were randomly selected; 1 for study group and another for control group to avoid contamination of the subjects. The number of adolescents in each class ranged from 30 – 40. There were 5 to 6 classes in each college. Simple random sampling technique (through lottery method) was used to select 30 samples each for study and control group.

Data collection

Institutional ethical committee approved the research proposal to conduct the study. Permission was obtained from Principals of each college. Written informed consent from parents and assent from subjects were also obtained before starting the study. A semi structured and self administered questionnaire was used to collect socio demographic data. Pre test with Loneliness Assessment scale, which is of 15 items, was conducted to assess loneliness among subjects. Cronbach's Alpha was found as 0.758 for the reliability of the study. Questionnaires were given

to all the students at a time in a single classroom. Filled Loneliness Assessment scale was collected back after 30 minutes. Degree of loneliness was assessed with score interpretation and categorized into low, moderate and high degree of loneliness. 21 sessions of art based therapy including 11 sessions of altered magazine photo and 10 sessions of crumpled paper painting was conducted for subjects. Each session was lasting for 45 minutes. Follow up was taken using same scale on 7th, 14th & 21st session. Post test was conducted on suppose to be 28th session for study group whereas pre and post test only were conducted for control group.

RESULTS

Data was collected from 30 participants each in study and control group. Socio - Demographic data of the subjects are depicted in Table 1.

In study group, 9 (30%) subjects were 15-16 years old and 21 (70%) were 17-19 years old; 20 (66.7%) were boys and 10 (33.3%) were girls. Educational status of father - 1 (3.3%) was no formal education, 3 (10%) were primary education, 15 (50%) were secondary education and 11 (36.7%) were graduate and above. Educational status of mother - 6 (20%) were no formal education, 2 (6.7%) were primary education, 14 (46.7%) were secondary education and 8 (26.7%) were graduate and above; Occupation of father - 3 (10%) were government employee, 13 (43.3%) were private employee, 7 (23.3%) were self employee and 7 (23.3%) were in others; Occupation of mother – no one was government employee, 5 (16.7%) were private employee, 4 (13.3%) were self employee and 21 (70%) were in others; Family income per month in Rupees. 2 (6.7%) were <2390, 2 (6.7%) were 2391 – 7101, 1 (3.3%) was 7102 – 11836, 4 (13.3%) were 11837 – 17755, 2 (6.7%) were 17756 – 23673, 14 (46.7%) were 23674 – 47347 and 5 (16.7%) were 47348 & above; 20 (66.7%) belong to Nuclear family and 10 (33.3%) belong to Joint family.

In control group, 13 (43.3%) subjects were 15-16 years old and 17 (56.7%) subjects were 17-19 years old. 15 (50%) were boys and 15 (50%) were girls. Educational status of father - 1 (3.3%) was no formal education, 4 (13.3%) were primary education, 17 (56.7%) were secondary education and 8 (26.7%) were graduate and above. Educational status of mother - 3 (10%) was no formal education, 5 (16.7%) were primary education, 15 (50%) were secondary education and 7 (23.3%) were graduate and above. Occupation of father - 2 (6.7%) were government employee, 9 (30%) were private employee, 10 (33.3%) were self employee and 9 (30%) were in others. Occupation of mother - 1 (3.3%) were government employee, no one was private employee, 6 (20%) were self employee and 23 (76.7%) were in others. Family income per month in Rupees – No one was <2390, 1 (3.3%) were 2391 – 7101, 4 (13.3%) was 7102 – 11836, 6 (20%) were 11837 – 17755, 5 (16.7%) were 17756 – 23673, 10 (33.3%) were 23674 – 47347 and 4 (13.3%) were 47348 & above. 9 (30%) belong to Nuclear family and 21 (70%) belong to Joint family.

Table 1: Socio Demographic data in experiment group and control group

Parameters		Experiment (%) (n=30)	Control (%) (n=30)	Chi-square P Value
Age (Yrs)	15 – 16	9 (30)	13 (43.3)	1.15 P=0.28
	17 – 19	21 (70)	17 (56.7)	
Gender	Male	20 (66.7)	15 (50)	1.71 P=0.19
	Female	10 (33.3)	15 (50)	
Educational status of father	No formal education	1 (3.3)	1 (3.3)	0.74 P=0.86
	Primary	3 (10)	4 (13.3)	
	Secondary	15 (50)	17 (56.7)	
	Graduate & above	11 (36.7)	8 (26.7)	
Educational status of mother	No formal education	6 (20)	3 (10)	2.38 P=0.50
	Primary	2 (6.7)	5 (16.7)	
	Secondary	14 (46.7)	15 (50)	
	Graduate & above	8 (26.7)	7 (23.3)	
Occupation of father	Government employee	3 (10)	2 (6.7)	1.70 P=0.64
	Private employee	13 (43.3)	9 (30)	
	Self employee	7 (23.3)	10 (33.3)	
	Others	7 (23.3)	9 (30)	
Occupation of mother	Government employee	0	1 (3.3)	-
	Private employee	5 (16.7)	0	
	Self employee	4 (13.3)	6 (20)	
	Others	21 (70)	23 (76.7)	
Family income per month (Rs)	<2390	2 (6.7)	0	-
	2391 – 7101	2 (6.7)	1 (3.3)	
	7102 – 11836	1 (3.3)	4 (13.3)	
	11837 – 17755	4 (13.3)	6 (20)	
	17756 – 23673	2 (6.7)	5 (16.7)	
	23674 – 47347	14 (46.7)	10 (33.3)	
	47348 & above	5 (16.7)	4 (13.3)	
Type of family	Nuclear	20 (66.7)	9 (30)	8.08 P=0.004
	Joint	10 (33.3)	21 (70)	
	No	17 (56.7)	20 (66.7)	

Degree of Loneliness

Out of 30 subjects, 6 (20%) had low degree of loneliness, 20 (66.7%) had moderate degree of loneliness and 4 (13.3%) had high degree of loneliness before intervention. I follow up was taken after 7th session of Art Based Therapy which shown 11 (36.7%) had low degree of loneliness, 16 (53.3%) had moderate degree of loneliness and 3 (10%) had high degree of loneliness. After 14th session in II follow up, 17 (56.7%) had low degree of loneliness, 13 (43.3%) had moderate degree of loneliness and no one had high degree of loneliness. 20 (66.7%) had low degree of loneliness, 10 (33.3%) had moderate degree of loneliness and no one had high degree of loneliness in III follow up after 21st session. Post test (suppose to be 28th session) results indicated that, all 30 (100%) had low degree of loneliness [Table 2 & Graph 1]

Table 2: Assess the degree of loneliness score among adolescents in experiment group

Degree of loneliness	Pre test (%)	Follow Up I (%)	Follow Up II (%)	Follow Up III (%)	Post-test (%)
15 – 30 (Low)	6 (20)	11 (36.7)	17 (56.7)	20 (66.7)	30 (100)
31 – 45 (Moderate)	20 (66.7)	16 (53.3)	13 (43.3)	10 (33.3)	0
46 – 60 (High)	4 (13.3)	3 (10)	0	0	0
Total	30 (100)	30 (100)	30 (100)	30 (100)	30 (100)

Graph 1: Bar diagram showing pre and post test degree of loneliness wise distribution of subjects in experimental group

Control group did not undergo any intervention. Data are depicted in Table 3 & Graph 2. 5 (16.7%) had low degree of loneliness, 22 (73.3%) had moderate degree of loneliness and 3 (10%) had high degree of loneliness in pre test whereas 5 (16.7%) had low degree of loneliness, 24 (80%) had moderate degree of loneliness and 1 (3.3%) had high degree of loneliness in post test.

Table 3: Assess the degree of loneliness score among adolescents in control group

Degree of loneliness	Pre test (%)	Post-test (%)
15 – 30 (Low)	5 (16.7)	5 (16.7)
31 – 45 (Moderate)	22 (73.3)	24 (80)
46 – 60 (High)	3 (10)	1 (3.3)
Total	30 (100)	30 (100)

Graph 2: Bar diagram showing pre and post test degree of loneliness wise distribution of subjects in control group

Table 4: Comparison of degree of loneliness score among adolescents in experiment and control group

Degree of loneliness score	Experiment (n=30)		Control (n=30)		MW test Z Value	P Value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Pre test	36.17	7.35	36.33	5.49	0.30	0.77
Post test	20.97	3.86	36.53	5.48	6.55	<0.0001

Table 5: Assess the effectiveness of Art Based Therapy on degree of loneliness score between pre-test and post-test in experimental group

Parameter	Degree of loneliness score			Wilcoxon Z Value	P Value
	Mean	SD	% change		
Pre test	36.17	7.35	-	-	-
Follow Up I	34.20	7.00	5.45	4.91	<0.0001
Follow Up II	30.47	6.64	15.76	4.80	<0.0001
Follow Up III	26.10	5.86	27.84	4.789	<0.0001
Post-test	20.97	3.86	42.02	4.788	<0.0001

Table 4 & 5 shows statistical significance in degree of loneliness after the intervention of Art Based Therapy since the p value is <0.0001.

Table 6: Assess the degree of loneliness score between pre-test and post-test in control group

Parameter	Degree of loneliness score			Wilcoxon Z Value	P Value
	Mean	SD	% change		
Pre test	36.33	5.49	-	-	-
Post-test	36.53	5.48	0.55	0.42	0.67

There is no statistical significance in degree of loneliness in control group since the p value is 0.67 [Table 6]

DISCUSSION

Mustafa Sahin^[8] found that becoming a cybervictim has a significant correlation with loneliness among adolescents. Ann H. Farrell et al^[9] reported that more than half of children and adolescents were experiencing at least moderate levels of loneliness. Similar to this, 20 (66.7%) adolescents had moderate degree of loneliness in current study.

Christina R. Victor & Keming Yang^[2] stated that those aged under 25 years and those aged over 65 years demonstrating the highest levels of loneliness. Poor physical health is associated with loneliness in young adult and midlife but not later life but in this study, 4 (13.3%) adolescents had high degree of loneliness.

Izabela Tabak & Dorota Zawadzka^[10] identified the number of participants who were addicted to the Internet was 11.6%, whereas 8.2% were at risk of addiction. 37.8% of the participants were moderately lonely, and 2.5% were severely lonely. They concluded that Internet addiction is a factor in predicting loneliness among adolescents, and overuse of the internet indirectly decreases the quality of life of young people, leading to emotional loneliness. The current study revealed that there is double the rate of moderate loneliness (66.7%) and a fivefold increase in high degree of loneliness (13.3%).

Anton Kall et al^[11] proposed that Internet-based Cognitive Behavior Therapy could be beneficial for alleviating loneliness; Merve Aydin^[12] found that group art therapy has a statistically significant impact on loneliness level among elderly adults who live alone. Art Based Therapy has been proven to be effective in reducing loneliness among adolescents in this study.

CONCLUSION

There was a statistically significant difference observed between the study and control group. Therefore, the findings duly support effectiveness of Art Based Therapy in alleviating loneliness among adolescents. It will boost their social skills as well as the self image.

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